

Mutations in the Spike Protein of SARS-COV-2 Variant, B.1.526 Occur at Two Phosphorylation Sites: Effects on Stability and Binding to ACE2 and DC-SIGN.

H.Y. Lim Tung and Pierre Limtung

Peptide and Protein Chemistry Research Laboratory, Nacbraht Biomedical Research Institute, New York City (Astoria), New York 11106, USA.

***Correspondence to:**

H.Y. Lim Tung

Peptide and Protein Chemistry Research Laboratory

Nacbraht Biomedical Research Institute

3164 21st Street, Suite 122

New York City (Astoria), NY 11106

USA

Tel: 332-201-7161

E mail: hyltung2010@nacbrahtbiomedresins.org

Abstract.

SARS-COV-2, the etiologic agent of COVID-19 is able to infect cells through its Spike protein (SPp) which must first bind to its receptor ACE2. Most currently developed vaccines target the SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein. Many SARS-COV-2 variants have been identified that exhibit several mutations in their Spike protein. SARS-COV-2 variant, B.1.526 was identified in New York, U.S.A. [Annavaiah, M.K. (2021) medRxiv, DOI: 10.1101/2020.02.23.21) and shown to contain the mutations, L5F, T95I, D253G, E484K, S477N, D614G and A701V. T95 and S477 of SPp are phosphorylation sites for a number of Protein kinases, including Cdk1 and GSK-3. Here, through Computerized Structure Model Analysis and Thermodynamic Calculations, it is shown that phosphorylations of T95 and S477 increases the stabilities of SARS-COV-2 encoded SPp-ACE2 and SPp-DC-SIGN complexes with very marginal effects on the binding efficiencies between the components of the complexes, and mutations T95I and S477N antagonize the effects of the phosphorylations of T95 and S477. Thus, it appears that SARS-COV-2 variant, B.1.526 has adapted to exploit the protein phosphorylation apparatus of its host cells to its advantage, and the effects of phosphorylation of T95 and S477 are blunted through random mutation. Whether Neutralizing Antibodies that target SPp can recognize the phosphorylated forms of SPp is currently unknown.

Introduction.

SARS-COV-2, the etiologic agent of COVID-19 [1-4] enters its host cells through the binding of its Spike protein (SPp) to the ACE2 protein. The interaction between SPp and ACE2 appears to be an obligate step in the infection and replication of SARS-COV-2 [3,5-10]. There is also a coordinated immune response against SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein [11-14]. The targeting of the SPp by either vaccination or specific drugs has therefore been an obvious goal in the control of SARS-COV-2 infection and virulence. Currently, most developed vaccines in use in the United States and elsewhere target SPp [15-20]. The choice of the SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein as a target for vaccination purpose is fraught with complications, including its high mutability. Indeed, many studies have now documented the emergence of several new strains of SARS-COV-2 with extensive mutations within the SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein. The identified strains include B.1.1.7 from the United Kingdom, B.1.351 from South Africa, P.1/P.2 from Brazil, B.1.526 from New York, U.S.A and B.1.6.17 from India have emerged [21-26]. In a number of cases, it has been argued that mutations in SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein attenuate the immune response by causing a decrease in the affinities of neutralizing antibodies which could affect viral load and disease progression [27,28]. Increase in the binding affinity of the SPp and ACE2 as a result of mutations has also been suggested [28-33].

The portion of SPp that mediates the attachment and entry into host cells of SARS-COV-2 consists of two subunits, S1 and S2. The receptor binding domain which is localized within the S1 subunit contains a receptor binding motif that binds to the peptidase domain of ACE2 receptor. After binding to the ACE2 receptor, the fusion peptide from S2 subunit is inserted into the cell membrane which promotes fusion with the viral membrane [6-10]. The interaction between the Receptor Binding Domain of S1 subunit of SPp (amino acids 306 to 527) and the peptidase domain (amino acids 19 to 615) is of interest because mutations that are observed in several SARS-COV-2 variants occur within the receptor binding domain of S1 [21-26, 31-33]. Of particular interest is the mutation of Serine 477 to Asparagine (S477N) SPp of the SARS-COV-2 variant, B.1.526 identified in New York [25]. Another mutation of interest that occurs in the SARS-COV-2 variant, B.1.526 is T95I

[25]. Although, the N Terminal Domain of SPp which harbors the T95I mutation does not appear to have direct contacts with ACE2, a recent report by Soh, W.T. et al. [34] has provided evidence that the NTD of SPp may be important in binding to L-SIGN and DC-SIGN receptors in the lungs where expression levels of ACE2 are low [34,35].

Threonine 95 and Serine 477 are phosphorylation sites for GSK-3 and Cdk1 [36-42]. Phosphorylations of Threonine 95 and Serine 477 can have profound effects on the binding of S1 to ACE2, L-SIGN and DC-SIGN. The effects of phosphorylation of T95 and S477 and the mutations, T95I and S477N on the stability of SPp and its binding to ACE2 and L-SIGN are investigated. The results show that (i) phosphorylation Serine 477 of SPp cause significant increase in the stabilities of SPp-ACE2 and SPp-DC-SIGN complexes with marginal effects on the binding efficiencies between the components of complexes. These results are discussed with respect to the use of SPp as immunogen/vaccine and its recognition by Neutralization Antibodies.

Methods.

The structure SPp-ACE2 complexes was based on the use of structure determinations of SPp by Wrobel et al. [10]. and the ectodomain of ACE2 by Shang, J. et al.[9] respectively. The structure of SPp-DC-SIGN complexes were based on on the use of structure determinations of SPp by Wrobel et al. [10]. and the ectodomain DC-SIGN by Feinberg, H. et al.[43] Phosphorylation of SARS-COV-2 Nucleocapsid protein (NCp) was performed with FoldX using the Build Model Program pursuant to Guerois, R. et al. and Schymkowitz, J. et al. [44,45]. Mutation of amino acid residues was performed with FoldX using the Build Model Program pursuant to Guerois, R. et al. and Schymkowitz, et al. [44,45]. Docking experiments to identify the SPp-ACE2 and SPp-DC-SIGN complexes were performed using the ZDOCK program pursuant to Pierce, B.G. et al. [46]. All structures were rendered, visualized and analyzed by the CCP4 Molecular Graphics Program Version 2.10.11 as described by Mc Nicolas, S. et al [47] and the ZMM Molecular Modeling Program as described by Garden, D.P and Zhorov, B.S. [48]. Determination and calculation of Stability Energy ($\Delta G_{\text{stability}}$ energy) of the protein complexes was performed using the Stability Program of FoldX as described by Guerois, et al. and Schymkowitz, et al. [44,45]. Binding Energy ($\Delta \Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ energy) of protein complex was determined and calculated using the Analyze Complex Program of FoldX as described by Guerois, et al. and Schymkowitz, et al. [44,45].

Binding Energy Difference ($\Delta\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy difference}}$) between phospho-protein complexes and dephospho-protein complexes pursuant to Teng, et al. and Nishi, et al. [50-52] from the equation: $\Delta\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy difference}} = \Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$ of phospho-protein complexes - $\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$ (binding energy of dephospho-protein complexes).

Results.

Examination of the primary structure of the Receptor Binding Domain of SAR-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) reveals that Threonine 95 is a phosphorylation site for GSK-3 and Cdk-1 and Serine 477 is also phosphorylation site for Cdk1 and GSK-3 [38-41] (Figure 1 and Figure 2). Interestingly, the Receptor Binding Domain of SARS-COV-1 encoded SPp does not contain phosphorylation site, S477 (Figure 3). Analysis of the primary structure of the Receptor Binding domains of SPp of SARS-COV-2 variant from New York (B.1.526) [25] shows that Threonine 95 is mutated to Isoleucine (T95I) and Serine 477 is mutated to Asparagine (S477N) (Figure 1 and Figure 2). Thus, the phosphorylations of SPp on Threonine 95 and Serine 477 are obliterated. in SPp of SARS-CoV-2 variant B.1.526. The consequence of obliteration of the phosphorylation sites T95 and S477 of SPp through mutations is unknown.

The effects of phosphorylating Threonine 95 and Serine 477 on the stability of SPp and its binding efficiency to ACE2 were determined by Structure Model Analysis and Thermodynamic Calculations. To study the effect of phosphorylation of S477 of SPp on the stability and binding efficiency of the components of the SPp-ACE2 complex, the structure determinations of SPp by Wrobel et al. [10] and ectodomain of ACE2 by Shang et al. [9] were used. The effects of phosphorylation of Threonine 95 and Serine 477 on the stability and binding efficiency of the components of SPp-DC-SIGN complex were studied by Docking experiments followed by Structure Model Analysis and Thermodynamic Calculations. The Stability Energy ($\Delta G_{\text{stability energy}}$) of the Reference complex (Unphosphorylated SPp-ACE2) was estimated to be ~964 Kcal/mol and the Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) between the components of the Reference Complex (Unphosphorylated SPp-ACE2) was estimated to be ~286 Kcal/mol (Table 1). In comparison, the Stability Energy ($\Delta G_{\text{stability energy}}$) of the complex consisting of SPp phosphorylated on Serine 477 and ACE2 was estimated to be ~964 Kcal/mol and the Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) between the components of the complex consisting of SPp phosphorylated on Serine 477 and

ACE2 was estimated to be ~287 Kcal/mol with a calculated Binding Energy Difference of ~ -1 Kcal/mol (Table 1). The rendered structure of the complex consisting of SPP phosphorylated on Serine 477 and ACE2 was not significantly altered when compared to the structure of the Reference Complex (Unphosphorylated SPP-ACE2) (compare Figure 3 with Figure 4). The Stability Energy ($\Delta G_{\text{stability energy}}$) of the complex consisting of SPP phosphorylated on Threonine 95 and ACE2 was estimated to be ~978 Kcal/mol and the Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) between the components of the complex consisting of SPP phosphorylated on Threonine 95 and ACE2 was estimated to be ~286 cCal/mol with a calculated Binding Energy Difference of ~0 KCal/mol (Table 1). The Stability Energy ($\Delta G_{\text{stability energy}}$) of the complex consisting of SPP phosphorylated on both Threonine 95 and Serine 477, and ACE2 was estimated to be ~980 Kcal/mol and the Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) between the components of the complex consisting of SPP phosphorylated on Threonine 95 and ACE2 was estimated to be ~286 Kcal/mol with a calculated Binding Energy Difference of ~0 Kcal/mol (Table 1). These results are consistent with the conclusion that phosphorylations of Threonine 95 and S477 of SPP caused a significant increase in the Stability of the SPP-ACE2 without significantly affecting binding efficiency between the 2 components of the complex. These results also suggest that mutation S477N will prevent the phosphorylation dependent increase of Stability of the SPP-ACE2.

The N terminal domain (NTD) of S1 subunit of SPP does not appear to form contacts with ACE2 [6,8,9]. Thus, its role in SARS-COV-2 Infection has received less attention. However, recent works by Soh, W.T. et al. [34] provide evidence that the NTD of SPP can be important in the lungs by its binding to the L-SIGN and DC-SIGN Receptors. The effects of phosphorylation of Threonine 95 and Serine 477 on the stability and binding efficiency of the components of SPP-DC-SIGN complex were studied by Docking experiments followed by Structure Model Analysis and Thermodynamic Calculations. To study the effect of phosphorylation of S477 of SPP on the stability and binding efficiency of the components of the SPP-DC-SIGN complexes, the structure determinations of SPP by Wrobel et al. [10] and ectodomain of DC-SIGN by Feinberg et al. [43] were used. As previously described by et al. [34], DC-SIGN interacted with the NTD of SPP and not the CTD of SPP (Figure 5 and Figure 6) . The Stability Energy ($\Delta G_{\text{stability energy}}$) of the Unphosphorylated SPP-DC-SIGN complex was estimated to be ~806 Kcal/mol and the Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) of un-phosphorylated SPP-DC-SIGN complex was estimated to be ~119

Kcal/mol. In comparison, the Stability energy($\Delta G_{\text{stability energy}}$) and the Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) of the phospho-T95-Spp-DC-SIGN complex was estimated to be ~823 Kcal/mol and ~119 Kcal/mol respectively (Table 1). The structure of the phospho-T95-Spp-DC-SIGN was not significantly altered (compare Figure 5 with Figure 6). The Stability energy($\Delta G_{\text{stability energy}}$) and the Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) of the phospho-T95 and phospho-S477-Spp-DC-SIGN complex was estimated to be ~821 Kcal/mol and ~119 Kcal/mol respectively (Table 1). These results are consistent with the view that phosphorylation of Threonine 95 of Spp enhance the stability of Spp-DC-SIGN complex without significantly affecting the binding efficiency between the components of the Spp-DC-SIGN complex. These results also suggest that mutation T95I will prevent the phosphorylation dependent increase of Stability of the Spp-ACE2.

Discussion.

In the present work, it is shown that the Spike protein in SARS-COV-2 variant from New York, USA, B.1.526 [25] contains two mutations that affect the phosphorylation sites located at Threonine 95 in the N Terminal Domain (NTD) and Serine 477 in the C Terminal Domain (CTD) of S1 subunit of Spp. The S1 subunit of Spp binds to the ACE2 through a Receptor Binding Domain (RBD) located in the CTD of Spp [5-10]. The function of the NTD of Spp has remained obscure. However, recent work by Soh, et al. [34] has shown that the NTD of Spp may serve to bind the L-SIGN and DC-SIGN receptors in the lungs and other tissues where expression of ACE2 is low. Thepaut, M. et al. [35] has shown that preventing the engagement of DC-SIGN receptors with a glycomimetic antagonist attenuates SARS-COV-2 infection.

The Protein kinases that phosphorylate Threonine 95 and Serine 477 of Spp include Cdk-1 and GSK-3 which are involved in the control of cell survival, cell maintenance, cell proliferation and cell death [38-42,53-62]. Here, it is shown that phosphorylations of T95 and S477 Spp are accompanied by significant increase in the stability of Spp-ACE2 and Spp-DC-SIGN complexes without significant effect on the binding efficiency between the components of Spp-ACE2 and Spp-DC-SIGN complexes. These results suggest that SARS-COV-2 has adapted to exploit the protein phosphorylation apparatus of its host cells to enhance the stabilities of Spp-ACE2 and Spp-DC-SIGN complexes. In counterpart, through random mutational events, the effects of phosphorylation of T95 and S477 of Spp are blunted, an example of the Newton's third third law

which stipulates that every action has an equal and opposite reaction. A Cellular Response Mechanism involving the phosphorylation dependent sequestration of SARS-COV-2 encoded Nucleocapsid protein (NCP) by Protein 14-3-3 has been described [63,64]. The sequestration of NCp by Protein 14-3-3 also involves Cdk-1 and GSK-3 [63,64]. In the case of NCp and Protein 14-3-3 complex, it appears that SARS-COV-2 counteracted the Cellular Response Mechanism through mutations of the phosphorylation sites.

It is well established that phospho-proteins are highly immunogenic and antibodies can be quite specific at differentiating dephos- and phospho-proteins [65]. Whether vaccines that are SPp proteins [15-20] can elicit Neutralization Antibodies [11-14] that recognize phospho-SPp is currently unknown. It would be quite important to determine whether Neutralization Antibodies are ineffective because they failed to recognize the phosphorylated forms of SPp. The opposite may also be true. Neutralization antibodies that recognize phospho-SPp may not recognize SPp that cannot be phosphorylated as a result of mutations as seen in SARS-COV-2 variant, B.1.526.

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	Stability Energy (ΔG) Kcal/mol	Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G$) Kcal/mol	Binding Energy Difference ($\Delta\Delta\Delta G$) Kcal/mol
Dephospho-Spp-ACE2 complex	~964	~286	~000
Phospho-serine 477-Spp-ACE2 complex	~964	~287	~1
Phospho-threonine 95-Spp-ACE2 complex	~978	~286	~0
Phospho-serine 477/threonine 95- Spp-ACE2 complex	~980	~286	~0
Dephospho-Spp-DC-SIGN complex	~806	~119	~000
Phospho-serine 477-Spp- DC-SIGN complex	~805	~119	~1
Phospho-threonine 95-Spp- DC-SIGN complex	~823	~119	~0
Phospho-serine 477/threonine 95- Spp-DC-SIGN complex	~821	~119	~0

Table 1. Thermodynamic calculations, including Stability ($\Delta G_{\text{stability}}$), Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) and Binding Energy Difference ($\Delta\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy difference}}$) that underlie the binding of dephospho-Spp-ACE2 and various phospho-Spp-ACE2 complexes, and dephospho-Spp-DC-SIGN and various phospho-DC-SIGN complexes.

	81	90	95	100	110
Wuhan, China (NC_045512)	NPVLPFNDGVYFAS	T	EKSNIIRGWIFGTTL		
New York, USA (B.1.526)	NPVLPFNDGVYFAS	I	EKSNIIRGWIFGTTL		
United Kingdom (B.1.1.7)	NPVLPFNDGVYFAS	T	EKSNIIRGWIFGTTL0		
South Africa (B.1.351)	NPVLPFNDGVYFAS	T	EKSNIIRGWIFGTTL		
Brazil (P1/P2)	NPVLPFNDGVYFAS	T	EKSNIIRGWIFGTTL		
India (B.1.617)	NPVLPFNDGVYFAS	T	EKSNIIRGWIFGTTL		
SARS-COV-1 (NC_004718)	NPVIPFKDGIYFAA	T	EKSNNVVRGWVFGTTL		

Figure 1. Protein Sequence Alignment of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein from Wuhan, China (NC_045512), New York, USA (B.1.526), United Kingdom (B.1.1.7), South Africa (B.1.351), Brazil (P1/P2), India (B.1.617) and SARS-COV-1 encoded Spike protein (). Only threonine 95 of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein from New York, USA (B.1.526) is mutated (T95I)

	480	470	477	480	520
Wuhan, China (NC_045512)	NLKP	FERDI	STEI	YQAG	<u>S</u> TPCNGVEGFNCYF
New York, USA (B.1.526)	NLKP	FERDI	STEI	YQAG	<u>N</u> TPCNGV <u>Q</u> GFNCYF
United Kingdom (B.1.1.7)	NLKP	FERDI	STEI	YQAG	<u>S</u> TPCNGVEGFNCYF
South Africa (B.1.351)	NLKP	FERDI	STEI	YQAG	<u>S</u> TPCNGVEGFNCYF
Brazil (P1/P2)	NLKP	FERDI	STEI	YQAG	<u>S</u> TPCNGVEGFNCYF
India (B.1.617)	NLKP	FERDI	STEI	YQAG	<u>S</u> TPCNGV <u>Q</u> GFNCYF
SARS-COV-1 (NC_004718)	KLRP	FERDIS	NVPF	SPD	<u>G</u> KPCTPP_ALNCYW

Figure 2. Figure 1. Protein Sequence Alignment of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein from Wuhan, China (NC_045512), New York, USA (B.1.526), United Kingdom (B.1.1.7), South Africa (B.1.351), Brazil (P1/P2), India (B.1.617) and SARS-COV-1 encoded Spike protein (). Only serine 477 of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein from New York, USA (B.1.526) is mutated (S477N).

Figure 3. Panel A: Ribbon structure of unphosphorylated SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (blue) and ACE2 complex (green) rendered as described in Method Section. The brown spheres represent dephospho S477. Panel B: Realistic rendering of unphosphorylated SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (grey) and ACE2 complex (orange)

Figure 4. Panel A: Ribbon structure of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated S477 (blue) and ACE2 complex (green) rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent phospho S477. Panel B: Realistic rendering of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on S477 (grey) and ACE2 complex (orange)

Figure 5. Panel A: Ribbon structure of unphosphorylated SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (blue) and DC-SIGN complex (orange) rendered as described in Method Section. The brown spheres represent dephospho S477. Panel B: Realistic rendering of unphosphorylated SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (grey) and DC-SIGN complex (orange).

Figure 6. Panel A: Ribbon structure of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on T95 (blue) and DC-SIGN complex (orange) rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent phospho-T95. B: Realistic rendering of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on S477 (grey) and DC-SIGN complex (orange)

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